

DATA SERVICES: SLOVENE EXPERIENCE

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Social Science Data Archives (ADP), Slovenia

Belgrade conference 2013

OUTLINE

1. History
2. First visible results
3. Present day issues
4. What we offer
5. Service for data users
6. Service for data depositors
7. Internal service: digital preservation
8. Conclusions

Incentives from the beginning (90-ties)

-
 Ljubljana school of empirical social research: Institute of social sciences in Ljubljana (50 + years of existence)
 - We started rescuing what remained of past research data, work on documentation.
 - Reconstructing the history of social research in the country.
-
 Existence of strong on-going academic and public national longitudinal data generation programmes (SJM, Youth, ADS)
 - Provides a condition for continuous supply of new data, core data acquisition and data processing routines are defined.
 - The first data catalogue was published soon, basic data distribution service activates.
-
 Regular cooperation in international comparative research programmes was (re)established
 - Personal contacts and access to live experiences of a modern data archive organisation
-
 CESSDA, IFDO and IASSIST support
 - Mentoring role of CESSDA members (E. Mochmann, B. Hausstein)
 - IASSIST conference participation (Outreach grants)

AS A CONSEQUENCES

- ❏ Core collection and basic service established
- ❏ Appealing offer right from the beginning as a demonstration of usefulness
 - We succeeded to attract mass users (students) and more demanding users / a base for further promotion
 - Strong ties with data producers were established: extensive support in data management offered
 - Funders were persuaded to supply basic financial support for continuous service + *ad hoc* new service development projects grants received

- ❏ Data archivist staff professionalised
 - Permanent position, regular formal and on the job training

Knowledge

- Mastering of the technology of that time: **DDI**

- ❏ Good practice in established data service followed
 - Resulted in early application for membership in CESSDA

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Establishment of data archive and launching of Web page/Nesstar (Situation in 2005)

SOME PRESENT DAY ISSUES

- ❏ Robust research data ecosystem needed
 - Funders' requirements clearly formulated in an open access national policy
 - Research data service is orienting towards offering advantages for data producers and users
- ❏ Cooperation in easing high quality access to governmental data
- ❏ Data publication metaphor. (compare M. A. Parsons, P.A. Fox: **Is Data Publication the Right Metaphor? Data Science Journal Vol. 12,2013**)
 - Persistent identifiers attached, versioning controlled
 - Links from/to other scientific publications (e.g. data citation)
 - Repository Harvesting and aggregation
 - Extended usage statistics
- ❏ Research data is a high class scientific object
 - Archived data that meet the criteria are regarded as equivalent to scientific publications by ARRS

WHAT WE OFFER

Approx. **700** study descriptions / **400** downloadable data

ACADEMIC SURVEYS

- SJM68 -> omnibus survey
- thematic series (*Highways in Slovenia, Youth, Military occupations*)

GOVERNMENT DATA – OFFICIAL STATISTICS, SORS

INTERNATIONAL SURVEYS

- ADP distributor of data (SI part of study)
- ADP distributor of metadata in local language and referrals
- support, guides

gesis

Leibniz-Institut
für Sozialwissenschaften

NSD EUROPEAN ELECTION DATABASE

CESSDA

UK • DATA
ARCHIVE

ICPSR | INTER-UNIVERSITY
CONSORTIUM FOR
POLITICAL AND
SOCIAL RESEARCH
A PARTNER IN
SOCIAL SCIENCE
RESEARCH

International research

European Values Study

SERVICE FOR DATA USERS

Viewing and browsing data and documentation of surveys

Slovenian Public Opinion 2010: European Social Survey

Study description Data description Materials and publications Download data

ADP - IDNo: SJM10

Main author(s):

Kurdija, Slavko
Malnar, Brina
Uhan, Samo
Hafner-Fink, Mitja
Štebe, Janez

Other co-workers >

Producer:

CJM - Center za raziskovanje javnega mnenja in množičnih komunikacij = Public Opinion and Mass Communication Research Centre (Ljubljana, Slovenia; 2011)

Funding agency:

Agencija za raziskovalno dejavnost Republike Slovenije = Slovenian Research Agency

Series:

- SJM/Slovensko javno mnenje = Slovene Public Opinion Survey**
The SJM survey closely resemble the type of a General Social Surveys known in other countries. Its aim is to provide the scientific community with the data about changes in subjective perceptions and attitudes of the general population. The topics which repeats from year to year beginning with 1968 are the evaluations of general and economic situation in society, interethnic relations in Slovenia and Yugoslavia, politics, ecology and religion. Beginning in 1989 a SJM survey adds a cross-national comparative perspective by adopting and replicating some of the most well-known international comparative surveys, regional Central and East European as well as global. Occasionally under the SJM title appears some specialised topical projects.

- ESS/European Social Survey**
The European Social Survey (ESS) is a multi-country survey covering over 20 nations. Its aim is to chart and explain the interaction between Europe's changing institutions and populations. The

Complete study description

Access to data:

study description | download data

Status of the study: 4 - Full Study XML DDI Codebook Data description questions text.

9: highest range, comparative research, influential population methodological excellence
Publication date: 2012

How to quote this study?

Kurdija, Slavko, Brina Malnar, Mitja Hafner-Fink and Janez Štebe. Slovenian Public Opinion 2010: European Social Survey. Ljubljana: Univerza na Ljubljani, Fakulteta za družbene vede = Faculty of Social Sciences, Institute for Public Opinion Research = Social Science Research Centre (distribution), 2012.

DATA CATALOG

DESCRIPTION TABULATION ANALYSIS

Dataset: [SJM082] Slovene Public Opinion 2008/2 : European social survey

Full Title
[SJM082] Slovene Public Opinion 2008/2 : European social survey

Subtitle
European social survey

Parallel Title
Slovensko javno mnenje 2008/2. Evropska družboslovna raziskava

Identification Number
sjm082-en

Authoring Entity

- Kurdija Slavko Affiliation: Univerza v Ljubljani = University of Ljubljana, Center za raziskovanje javnega mnenja in množičnih komunikacij
- Malnar, Brina Affiliation: Univerza v Ljubljani = University of Ljubljana, Center za raziskovanje javnega mnenja in množičnih komunikacij
- Hafner Fink, Mitja Affiliation: Univerza v Ljubljani = University of Ljubljana, Center za raziskovanje javnega mnenja in množičnih komunikacij
- Uhan, Samo Affiliation: Univerza v Ljubljani = University of Ljubljana, Center za raziskovanje javnega mnenja in množičnih komunikacij
- Štebe, Janez Affiliation: Univerza v Ljubljani = University of Ljubljana, Center za raziskovanje javnega mnenja in množičnih komunikacij

Other identifications and acknowledgments

- Toš, Niko Affiliation: Univerza v Ljubljani = University of Ljubljana, Center za raziskovanje javnega mnenja in množičnih komunikacij

raziskava

- [SJM081] Slovene Public Opinion 2008/1 : European Values Survey
- [SJM082] Slovene Public Opinion 2008/2 : European social survey
- [SJM091] Slovenian Public Opinion 2009/1 : Religion, ISSP 2008 and Social Inequality, ISSP 2009
- [SJM092] Slovenian Public Opinion 2009/2 : National and International Security Survey
- [SJM10-en] Slovenian Public Opinion 2010

Dataset: [SJM10-en] Slovenian Public Opinion 2010

Variable G1 : Bil sem vesel in dobre volje.

PreQuestion Text
Prebral vam bom nekaj izjav o tem, kako se morda počutite v zadnjem času. Za vsako posebej povejte, kako pogosto ste se tako počutili v zadnjih dveh tednih.

Literal Question
G1 Bil sem vesel in dobre volje.

Values	Categories	N	%
1	ves čas	140	10.0%
2	večino časa	574	41.1%
3	več kot polovico časa	406	29.0%
4	manj kot polovico časa	156	11.2%
5	le malo časa	111	7.9%
6	nikoli	11	0.8%
8	ne vem	3	
9	b.o.	2	

Summary Statistics

Valid cases 1398
Missing cases 5
Minimum 1.0
Maximum 6.0
This variable is numeric

SERVICE FOR DATA USERS

- Easy online registration
- SEARCH

Search criteria: [Help](#)

Study Descripti: Study Description

Geographic Coverage
Geographic Unit
Unit of Analysis
Universe
Kind of Data
Methodology and Processing
Data Collection Methodology
Time Method
Sampling Procedure
Mode of Data Collection
Weighting

Return what?

Search for datasets
 Search for variables
 Search for tables

Data Access
Data Use Statement
Location
Variable Description
Variable Name
Question Text
Variable Label
Variable Concept
Category Label

More Less

Search

Registration to access data

Dear users!
Please, complete the registration form below.
After confirmation you will receive username and password on your email.
Additional information is available in *Help with completing the registration form and Materials on demand*.

Help with completing the registration form
Materials on demand
Forgot your password?

Fields marked with * are required.

First name*:
Last name*:
Address*:
Postcode and city*:
User category*:
Organization:
Taxpayer:
VAT number:
Telephone:
Fax:
Email address*:

Yes

Select purpose of the use of material. You can choose between *educational*, *scientific*, *commercial* and *public* purpose.

Purpose of the use*:
Select how you are going to use the material. You can choose between *online data analysis* or *downloading data*. In the latter case you have to analyse data in a suitable statistical program.

I will*:
Please, specify the purpose of the use*:
(150 to 500 characters)

- Help desk with several manuals published on-line
- Workshops and presence at conferences and summer schools

- Partnership with similar institutions

SERVICE FOR DATA DEPOSITORS

- ❏ Counselling, guidelines, tools such as Metadata editor, processing and preparation of acquisition

DDI Metadata Editor (Nesstar Publisher)

The IHSN Metadata Editor, also known as the Nesstar Publisher, is a specialized XML editor compliant with the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) 2.n and the Dublin Core metadata standards

Number	Name	Label	Width	StartCol	EndCol
v7	w2_a_intrv_m	a14_m - Date of interview	2	21	22
v8	w2_a_intrv_y	a14_y - Date of interview	4	23	26
v9	w2_a_intrvart	a15 - Interview start time	4	27	30
v10	w2_a_refusal	a22 - Reason for refusal	2	31	32
v11	w2_a_refint	a23 - Degree of interact	2	33	34
v12	w2_a_dob_m	b1_m - Date of birth (m)	2	35	36
v13	w2_a_dob_y	b1_y - Date of birth (y)	4	37	40
v14	w2_a_gen	b2 - Gender	2	41	42

OBRAZEC ZA OPIS RAZISKAVE

Pričujoči obrazec temelji na vsebinskih opredelitvah iz mednarodnega Standardnega opisa raziskave (<http://www.icpsr.umich.edu/DDI/>). Izpolnjujete lahko s pomočjo navadnega urejevalnika besedila. Cel dokument je razdeljen na štiri osnovna poglavja: opis vsebine raziskave, opis datotek, opis spremljivk in opis spremljajočega gradiva. Pričujoči Obrazec je namenjen predvsem opisu prvega poglavja. Priporočamo, da se pri izpolnjevanju zgljedujete pri domačih že zaključenih opisih raziskav v XML <http://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/opisi/index.xml>.

Možno je tudi direktno izpolnjevanje XML dokumenta, za kar potrebujete poseben urejevalnik besedila, ki to podpira. Ta postopek je zelo primeren za raziskave v seriji, kjer je potrebnih le malo popravkov in lahko za osnovo vzamemo opis predhodne raziskave. V kolikor se za to odločite, vam v ADP nudimo vso potrebno pomoč.

Opis raziskave naj bo narejen tako v slovenskem kot angleškem jeziku.

Opis raziskave <studyDesc>

Naslov, avtor, izdelava in distribucija <citation>

<pubStmt>
Naslov Zabeležite naslov raziskave. Npr. *Slovensko javno mnenje 1999/4* <tit>

</tit>
Podnaslov Zabeležite podnaslov raziskave. Npr. *Stališča o pridruženju Evropski Uniji* <subTit>

</subTit>
Naslov v drugem jeziku Naslov v angleškem jeziku. V kolikor je originalni naslov v tujem jeziku navedite tudi tega. Npr. *Slovene Public Opinion Survey 1999/4 : Attitudes on Integration in the European Union* <parTit>

</parTit>
 </titStmt>

Odgovornost <rspStmt>

SERVICE FOR DATA DEPOSITORS

- Service provider – infrastructural center
- Evaluation of received materials
- Bibliographic reference

Bibliografije raziskovalcev

2.20 Zaključena znanstvena zbirka podatkov ali korpus

40. ADAM, Frane, KRISTAN, Primož, VOJVODIČ, Ana, RONČEVIČ, Borut, KALČIČ, Špela, PODMENIK, Dane, LAMUT, Urša, BESEDNJAK VALIČ, Tamara. *RAZJED10 - Lokalna in regionalna razvojna jedra = [Local and regional developmental cores] : [datoteka podatkov]*. Ljubljana: Fakulteta za družbene vede, Arhiv družboslovnih podatkov, [2010].

<http://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/opisi/razjed10/>. [COBISS.SI-ID [29428061](#)]

kategorija: 2H (Z2); tipologijo je verificiral OSICD

točke: 3.75, št. avtorjev: 8

41. MAKAROVIČ, Matej, RONČEVIČ, Borut, TOMŠIČ, Matevž, BESEDNJAK VALIČ, Tamara. *Slovenski utrip 1/2010 : družba znanja*. Ljubljana: Fakulteta za družbene vede, Arhiv družboslovnih podatkov, 2010. <http://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/opisi/sutr1001/>. [COBISS.SI-ID [1024194881](#)]

kategorija: 2H (Z2); tipologijo je verificiral OSICD

točke: 7.5, št. avtorjev: 4

- Potential expansion to areas that are far less represented, including Quali-data, ethnology, economics, pedagogy, psychology etc.

INTERNAL SERVICE: DIGITAL PRESERVATION

DEVELOPMENT OF APPLICATION ON THE TOP OF FEDORA

PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER (URN)

USING SECOND LOCATION

THOMSON REUTERS

CERTIFICATION (DSA) AND INCLUSION IN REPOSITORIES

Controlled Vocabularies

DDI-Codebook

The current version of DDI-C is [2.5](#).

DDI-Lifecycle

[DDI 3.1](#)

DEVELOPMENT

URN (UNIFORM RESOURCE NAME)

URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:_____

URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SURVEYID

TYPE

VERSION_REVISION

Type of materials	Suggested appendix	Example
Related materials	<u>_RM1_V1_R1</u>	URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SJM011_RM1_V1_R1
Related publications	<u>_RP1_V1_R1</u>	URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SJM011_RP1_V1_R1
Other material	<u>_OM1_V1_R1</u>	URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SJM011_OM1_V1_R1
Data file	<u>_D1_V1_R1</u>	URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SJM011_D1_V1_R1
Questionnaire	<u>_Q1_V1_R1</u>	URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SJM011_Q1_V1_R1
Code list	<u>_CL1_V1_R1</u>	URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SJM011_CL1_V1_R1
Syntax	<u>_SY1_V1_R1</u>	URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SJM011_SY_V1_R1
Licence agreement	<u>_LA1_V1_R1</u>	URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SJM011_LA_V1_R1

Using two major system functions: the **URN generator** – service defining unique URN record for every object and the **URN resolver** – interpreter that connects a given URN record with a digital object.

PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER

License Agreement in ADP

- **Depositor** (name, institution, position)
- Name of a **survey**
- **Confidentiality** agreement / own copy
- **Copyright (CC + _____)**
- **Terms of Use** in order to protect the confidentiality of data

Enters into force when **depositor** sign the agreement.

Attached – list of deposited materials.

Youth 2010 is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 2.5 Slovenia License](#).
Based on a work at www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si.

CONCLUSIONS

- ❏ Organisational consolidation
 - Human resources (6 people + students support)
 - Active promotion of service
 - Regular presentations and workshops for users, conference presentations
- ❏ New CESSDA
 - National service requirements need to be fulfilled
 - A framework for cooperation in common activities and projects
- ❏ Contribute to the national action plan for OPEN RESEARCH DATA based on OECD and EU initiatives
- ❏ National networking activities
 - ESFRI and national research infrastructures
 - Open access information point, institutional repository infrastructure building, NUK and dLib
 - SORS, AS, ...

**If you have questions about access to data or data archiving
please contact us at**

<http://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/>

E-mail: arhiv.podatkov@fdv.uni-lj.si

